

A comparison between Rice's Theorem and Rogers' Fixed Point Theorem and related notions

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Abstract. In this paper we compare two classical results of Recursion Theory, namely, Rice's Theorem and Rogers' Fixed Point Theorem, showing that, in the context of *universal programming systems*, the former is *strictly weaker* than the latter. Moreover, we introduce the notions of *effectively uniformly non-trivial sequence of classes of partial recursive functions* and *diagonal set of a sequence of classes of partial recursive functions*, that generalize the notions of non-trivial class of partial recursive functions and of index set of a class of partial recursive functions, respectively. We show, in particular, that Rogers' Fixed Point Theorem is equivalent to the condition that the diagonal sets of the effectively uniformly non-trivial sequences of classes of partial recursive functions are recursively inseparable. As a consequence, some generalizations of Rice's Theorem are obtained.

We also present some properties concerning recursive isomorphisms of diagonal sets (of effectively uniformly non-trivial sequences of classes of partial recursive functions). Specifically, we show that every recursively enumerable diagonal set is a creative set, and that the isomorphism type of the diagonal sets is strictly larger than the isomorphism type of the index sets of non-trivial classes of partial recursive functions. Additional (non-)recursiveness properties of the diagonal sets are presented and discussed as well.

Keywords: Rice's Theorem, Rogers' Fixed Point Theorem, Diagonal sets, Sequences of classes of partial recursive functions

1 Introduction

Rice's Theorem (RT) [4, p. 34] characterizes a wide class of non-recursive subsets of \mathbb{N} , the set of natural numbers. Given an *acceptable programming system* φ ,¹ the statement of RT says that, for all classes \mathcal{C} of partial recursive functions, the set $I = \{x \in \mathbb{N} : \varphi_x \in \mathcal{C}\}$ —the *index set* of \mathcal{C} —is non-recursive iff \mathcal{C} is *non-trivial*, namely, there exist partial recursive functions φ_m and φ_n such that $\varphi_m \in \mathcal{C}$ and $\varphi_n \notin \mathcal{C}$. In such a case, the functions φ_m and φ_n are *witnesses* of the condition that \mathcal{C} is non-trivial.

¹ See Section 2 for a definition of the standard notion of (acceptable) programming system as well as for other basic notions of Recursion Theory used in this paper.

Most proofs of RT present in the literature consist in *reducing* the well known *halting set* $K = \{x \in \mathbb{N} : \varphi_x(x) \text{ is defined}\}$ (or its complement) to the index set \mathbf{I} above. Since K is non-recursive, *by reduction*, \mathbf{I} turns out to be non-recursive as well. Proofs based on reduction often use *Kleene's s-m-n Theorem* (see Proposition 1.(B)). However, in the literature there are also alternative proofs of RT that do not use reduction. This is the case, in particular, of the easy and elegant proof of RT reported in [1, Theorem 1.6., p. 203], which is a typical *proof by diagonalization* based on *Rogers' Fixed Point Theorem* (RFPT) [4, Theorem I, p. 180]. RFPT is another classical result of Recursion Theory which has several important applications. Given an acceptable programming system φ , the statement of RFPT says that, for all recursive functions r , there exists an index q —a *fixed point of r* —such that $\varphi_q = \varphi_{r(q)}$.² Let us briefly review the steps involved in the proof of RT presented in [1]. Starting from the assumption that the class \mathcal{C} is non-trivial but that its index set \mathbf{I} is recursive, and letting m and n be any two indices such that $\varphi_m \in \mathcal{C}$ and $\varphi_n \notin \mathcal{C}$, a function r is defined such that $r(x) = n$, for $x \in \mathbf{I}$, and $r(x) = m$, for $x \notin \mathbf{I}$. Since \mathbf{I} is recursive, r turns out to be a recursive function, and hence RFPT provides a fixed point q of r . But then we have that $\varphi_q \in \mathcal{C}$ iff $\varphi_q = \varphi_{r(q)} \notin \mathcal{C}$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, if \mathcal{C} is non-trivial, its index set \mathbf{I} must be a non-recursive set.

The only property of φ that is used in the above proof is that (the statement of) RFPT holds for φ . No other additional property of φ (such as the *s-m-n Theorem*) is needed.³ And in fact, there exist *non-trivial* programming systems which are not acceptable but for which, however, RFPT holds (see Remark 1). Thus, for each of these programming systems, RT holds as well.

In this paper we show that, in the context of universal programming systems, RT is *strictly weaker* than RFPT, namely, there exist universal programming systems for which RT holds but RFPT does not hold. (To our knowledge, there is no proof of this fact in the literature.) Moreover, we introduce the notions of *effectively uniformly non-trivial sequence of classes of partial recursive functions* and of *diagonal set of a sequence of classes of partial recursive functions*, that generalize, respectively, the notions of non-trivial class of partial recursive functions and of index set of a class of partial recursive functions, and show that RFPT is equivalent to the condition that the diagonal sets of the above sequences are recursively inseparable, thereby characterizing RFPT (see Section 3). As a consequence, generalizations of Rice's Theorem are obtained.

² In the literature, this statement is commonly attributed to S. C. Kleene and the corresponding theorem for acceptable programming systems (i.e., RFPT) is often identified with *Kleene's (second) Recursion Theorem*. However, Kleene's original statement of his Recursion Theorem (see Proposition 1.(C)) is different than that of Rogers above; but, in the context of acceptable programming systems, the two statements are in fact *equivalent* (though Rogers' statement is *strictly weaker* than Kleene's in the more general case of universal programming systems [3]).

³ Properties like the *s-m-n Theorem* are sometimes called *control structures* in the literature (see, for instance, [3] and [5]). These include also Kleene's Recursion Theorem and Rogers' Fixed Point Theorem, to cite just a few.

Intuitively, a sequence of classes of partial recursive functions is effectively uniformly non-trivial if each class of the sequence is non-trivial and, moreover, (the indices of) two partial recursive functions witnessing this condition can be determined effectively from any index of the class in the sequence. Given an acceptable programming system φ , the diagonal set of a sequence $\mathcal{C}_0, \mathcal{C}_1, \dots$ of classes of partial recursive functions is the set of the indices $x \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\varphi_x \in \mathcal{C}_x$.⁴ (See Section 4 for formal definitions of these notions.)

Besides the characterization of RFPT mentioned above, we present further properties of the diagonal sets (of effectively uniformly non-trivial sequences of classes of partial recursive functions); in particular, we will see that the recursively enumerable (r.e.) diagonal sets are precisely the creative sets and that the isomorphism type of the diagonal sets is strictly larger than the isomorphism type of the index sets of non-trivial classes of partial recursive functions (see Section 4.1). Additional (non-)recursiveness properties of the diagonal sets are presented and discussed as well (see the Appendix).

2 Notations and terminology

For (basic) notions and properties of Recursion Theory used in this paper but not reviewed here we refer to [4]. \mathbb{N} denotes the set of the natural numbers $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ and \mathbb{E} the set of the even numbers $\{0, 2, 4, \dots\}$. For $n \geq 1$, we denote with $\mathcal{P}^{(n)}$ and $\mathcal{R}^{(n)}$ the classes of the n -ary partial recursive functions and n -ary recursive functions, respectively. The class of the recursive (resp., non-recursive) sets is denoted with **Rec** (resp., **NRec**). The *predecessor function* **pre** is the 1-ary function such that **pre**(0) = 0 and **pre**($x+1$) = x , for each $x \in \mathbb{N}$. The domain and the range of a function f are denoted with **Dom**(f) and **Ran**(f), respectively. The *nowhere defined function*, i.e., the function with empty domain, is denoted with \perp . Given two functions f and g , we write $f \leq g$ if **Dom**(f) \subseteq **Dom**(g) and **Ran**(f) \subseteq **Ran**(g) (the negation of $f \leq g$ will be written as $f \not\leq g$); moreover, we denote with $f \circ g$ the composition of f with g . A subset S of \mathbb{N} is *non-trivial* if $S \neq \emptyset$ and $\overline{S} \neq \emptyset$, where $\overline{S} =_{\text{Def}} \mathbb{N} \setminus S$ is the *complement* of S .

A 1-ary bijective recursive function is called a *recursive permutation*. A set S is *recursively isomorphic to a set* T , in symbols $S \equiv T$, if there exists a recursive permutation j such that $S = j^{-1}(T)$, i.e., S is the *inverse image* (or *preimage*) of T under j . In such a case we say that S is recursively isomorphic to T via j . For each class \mathbf{C} of subsets of \mathbb{N} , the (*recursive*) *isomorphism type* of \mathbf{C} is the class $\text{Iso}(\mathbf{C}) =_{\text{Def}} \{S \subseteq \mathbb{N} : S \equiv T \text{ for some } T \in \mathbf{C}\}$.

We will use the *lambda notation* " $\lambda x_1 x_2 \dots x_n. E$ " to represent n -ary functions as well as n -ary predicates, where the variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n range over \mathbb{N} and the *expression* E contains no *free variables* other than possibly x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n . For example, $\lambda xy.(x+1)$ represents the 2-ary (total) function that maps the ordered pair of numbers (x, y) to the successor of x . As usual, the logical symbols

⁴ However, we will consider diagonal sets relative to any programming system, not only the acceptable φ 's.

“ \neg ”, “ \wedge ”, “ \vee ”, “ \implies ” and “ \iff ” denote negation, conjunction, disjunction, implication and equivalence of propositions. Likewise, “ $(\exists x)$ ” and “ $(\forall x)$ ” denote existential and universal quantifiers, respectively, where the quantified variable x is intended to range over \mathbb{N} . The *minimalisation operator* is denoted with “ μx ” [1, Corollary 5.3.]. For all 1-ary functions f , we put $f^{-1} =_{\text{Def}} \lambda x. \mu y (f(y) = x)$.

We let π stand for a fixed *recursive pairing function* (e.g., $\lambda xy. 2^x(2y+1) - 1$, see [1, proof of Theorem 1.2.(a)]) and denote with π' and π'' the inverses of π .⁵

Let $S, T \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. The pair (S, T) is *recursively inseparable*, in symbols $S \bowtie T$, if there is no a recursive set R which *separates* S from T , i.e., such that $S \subseteq R \subseteq \overline{T}$.

Given two n -ary functions f and g and an n -ary predicate P , where $n \geq 1$, we denote with $[P ? f : g]$ the n -ary function h such that, for each n -tuple \mathbf{x} of natural numbers, if $P(\mathbf{x})$ holds, then $h(\mathbf{x}) = f(\mathbf{x})$; otherwise, if $P(\mathbf{x})$ does not hold, then $h(\mathbf{x}) = g(\mathbf{x})$.⁶ Also, we put $[P ? f] =_{\text{Def}} [P ? f : \perp]$.

We will sometimes use the following forms of *primitive recursion* to define functions. We recall that, given a 1-ary function f , a 3-ary function g , a 2-ary function h , and a number n , there exist unique functions u and v such that

$$\begin{cases} u(x, 0) = f(x) \\ u(x, y + 1) = g(x, y, u(x, y)) \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} v(0) = n \\ v(x + 1) = h(x, v(x)), \end{cases}$$

for all $x, y \in \mathbb{N}$. We will denote these functions u and v with $\text{PrimRec}(f, g)$ and $\text{PrimRec}^*(n, h)$, respectively.

A *programming system* (ps) is just a 2-ary partial recursive function ϕ [5]. A ps ϕ is *universal* if $\{\phi_x : x \in \mathbb{N}\} = \mathcal{P}^{(1)}$, where $\phi_x =_{\text{Def}} \lambda y. \phi(x, y)$ for $x \in \mathbb{N}$; ϕ is *non-trivial* if $(\exists x)(\phi_x \neq \phi_0)$.

Let ϕ be a ps. Given an n -ary function f , where $n \geq 1$, we put $\phi \Downarrow f =_{\text{Def}} \lambda x_1 x_2 \dots x_n y. \phi(f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), y)$.⁷ A ps ψ is *effectively translatable* into ϕ [5] if $\psi = \phi \Downarrow t$, for some recursive function $t \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$. For all $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, we define $\langle r \rangle_\phi =_{\text{Def}} \{x \in \mathbb{N} : \phi_x = \phi_{r(x)}\}$. Members of the set $\langle r \rangle_\phi$ are called *ϕ -fixed points* of r . A *ϕ -index set* is a subset S of \mathbb{N} such that, for all $x, y \in \mathbb{N}$, if $x \in S$ and $\phi_x = \phi_y$, then $y \in S$. Given a class \mathcal{C} of partial recursive functions, we put $\mathbf{I}_\phi^{\mathcal{C}} =_{\text{Def}} \{x \in \mathbb{N} : \phi_x \in \mathcal{C}\}$ (the *ϕ -index set of \mathcal{C}*). For all partial recursive functions f , we will abbreviate $\mathbf{I}_\phi^{\{f\}}$ as \mathbf{I}_ϕ^f .

An *acceptable programming system* (aps) is a ps φ such that, every ps is effectively translatable into φ , i.e., $\mathcal{P}^{(2)} = \{\varphi \Downarrow r : r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}\}$ [5].

The following proposition states some basic results of Recursion Theory that we will use throughout the paper (see [4]).

Proposition 1. *For all apses φ , properties (A)–(F) below hold.*

⁵ Thus, we have that $\pi'(\pi(x, y)) = x$, $\pi''(\pi(x, y)) = y$, and $\pi(\pi'(z), \pi''(z)) = z$, for all $x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}$.

⁶ Note that, in this paper we adopt the following convention: given two functions u and v and two respective arguments \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{z} , we regard the condition “ $u(\mathbf{y}) = v(\mathbf{z})$ ” as true exactly when, either $\mathbf{y} \in \text{Dom}(u)$, $\mathbf{z} \in \text{Dom}(v)$ and the numbers $u(\mathbf{y})$ and $v(\mathbf{z})$ are equal, or $\mathbf{y} \notin \text{Dom}(u)$ and $\mathbf{z} \notin \text{Dom}(v)$.

⁷ Observe that, for all $r, s \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, $(\phi \Downarrow r) \Downarrow s = \phi \Downarrow (r \circ s)$ and $(\forall x)(\phi_{r(x)} = (\phi \Downarrow r)_x)$.

- (A) There exists a recursive function $\text{conv} \in \mathcal{R}^{(3)}$ —called a convergence predicate for φ —such that $\mathbf{Ran}(\text{conv}) \subseteq \{0, 1\}$ and, for all $x, y \in \mathbb{N}$, we have that $y \in \mathbf{Dom}(\varphi_x) \iff (\exists z)(\text{conv}(x, y, z) = 1)$.
- (B) For all $n \geq 1$ and $\psi \in \mathcal{P}^{(n+1)}$, there exists $s \in \mathcal{R}^{(n)}$ such that $\varphi \Downarrow s = \psi$ (*s-m-n Theorem*).
- (C) For all *pses* ϕ , there exists an $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\varphi_n = \phi_n$ (*Kleene's Recursion Theorem*).
- (D) There exists a recursive function $\text{pad} \in \mathcal{R}^{(2)}$ —called a padding function for φ —such that $(\forall x)(\forall y)((\varphi_{\text{pad}(x,y)} = \varphi_x) \wedge (\text{pad}(x,y) > y))$.
- (E) For all $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(2)}$, there exists a recursive function $\text{fix} \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $(\forall x)(\varphi_{\text{fix}(x)} = \varphi_{r(x, \text{fix}(x))})$ (*Fixed Point Theorem with Parameters*).
- (F) For all *aps* ξ , there exists a recursive permutation j such that $\varphi = \xi \Downarrow j$ (*Rogers' Isomorphism Theorem*).

The notion of a recursively inseparable pair of sets admits the following “effective” version. Let ϕ be a *ps* and let $S, T \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. (S, T) is a *Kleene pair* with respect to ϕ [6], and we write $S \bowtie_{\phi} T$, if there exists $k \in \mathcal{R}^{(2)}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} (\forall x)(\forall y) \left(k(x, y) \in (\mathbf{Dom}(\phi_x) \setminus \mathbf{Dom}(\phi_y)) \implies k(x, y) \in T \right. \\ \left. \wedge k(x, y) \in (\mathbf{Dom}(\phi_y) \setminus \mathbf{Dom}(\phi_x)) \implies k(x, y) \in S \right) \end{aligned}$$

holds. In such a case, we say that k is a *Kleene function* for (S, T) relative to ϕ .

A set S is ϕ -*productive* [1], where ϕ is a *ps*, if there exists $p \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that

$$(\forall x)(\mathbf{Dom}(\phi_x) \subseteq S \implies p(x) \in (S \setminus \mathbf{Dom}(\phi_x))).$$

In such a case, p is called a ϕ -*productive function* for S . S is ϕ -*creative* [1] if S is r.e. and its complement is ϕ -productive. It can be verified that, for all *apses* φ , if a set S is φ -creative then $S \equiv \overline{I_{\varphi}^{\perp}}$ (see [4, Exercise 7-32.] and [1, Example 3.9.]).

A *sequence of classes of partial recursive functions* is a function \mathcal{C} which maps each natural number x to a class $\mathcal{C}(x)$ of partial recursive functions. We will write $\mathcal{C}(x)$ as \mathcal{C}_x , for each $x \in \mathbb{N}$.

Note. In the sequel we will refer to a sequence of classes of partial recursive functions simply as a sequence. This will cause no confusion.

Throughout the paper ϑ denotes a fixed *aps*.

3 RT vs RFPT

In this section, after reviewing the formal statements of when RT and RFPT hold for a (not necessarily acceptable) *ps* ϕ (cf. Definition 1), we show that RT is strictly weaker than RFPT (cf. Theorem 4).

Definition 1. Let ϕ be a *ps*.

- (1) RT holds for ϕ , if every non-trivial ϕ -index set is non-recursive.⁸
(2) RFPT holds for ϕ , if $\langle r \rangle_\phi \neq \emptyset$, for all $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$.

For $S \in \{\text{RT}, \text{RFPT}\}$, we denote with \mathcal{H}^S the class of the pses ϕ such that S holds for ϕ . Using these notations we can restate succinctly Rice's and Rogers' theorems for apses φ recalled in the introduction:

Theorem 1 (Rice's Theorem). *For all apses φ , $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RT}}$.*

Theorem 2 (Rogers' Fixed Point Theorem). *For all apses φ , $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$.*

Remark 1. Plainly, there exist non-universal non-trivial pses ϕ such that $\phi \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$. A simple example is $\phi =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda xy. (\vartheta_x \neq \perp) ? \lambda xy. 0]$.

As observed in Section 1, we have that RFPT implies RT; formally:

Theorem 3. $\mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}} \subseteq \mathcal{H}^{\text{RT}}$.

However, we prove that the converse does not hold. Specifically, we have:

Theorem 4. *There exists a universal ps ψ such that $\psi \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RT}} \wedge \psi \notin \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$.*

Proof. We will first construct two pses ω and σ such that: (I) ω is universal; (II) $\omega \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$; and (III) $(\forall x)(\omega_x \neq \sigma_x)$. Then, we will use ω and σ to define the ps ψ sought for. Preliminarily, let $\zeta =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda x. (x = 0) ? \lambda x. 0]$ and let $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{N}$ be such that $\vartheta_{\mathbf{z}} = \zeta$. Moreover, let $\theta =_{\text{Def}} \lambda x. \vartheta(x, 0)$. Clearly, θ is a partial recursive function. We define $\sigma =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda xy. ((\theta(x) = \mathbf{z}) \vee (y = 0)) ? \lambda xy. 0]$ and

$$\omega =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda xy. ((\theta(x) = \mathbf{z}) \wedge (y = 0)) ? \lambda xy. 0 : [\lambda xy. ((\vartheta \Downarrow \theta)_x \not\leq \zeta) ? \vartheta \Downarrow \theta]].$$

Plainly, $\omega, \sigma \in \mathcal{P}^{(2)}$.

Claim 4.1. ω is universal.

Proof. Let $f \in \mathcal{P}^{(1)}$. We must prove that there exists $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\omega_n = f$. The following two cases arise.

Case 1) $f = \zeta$. In this case, we let n be such that $\vartheta_n = \lambda x. \mathbf{z}$.

Case 2) $f \neq \zeta$. In this case, we let n be such that $\vartheta_n = \lambda x. m$, where $m \in \mathbf{I}_{\vartheta}^f$. \square

Claim 4.2. $\omega \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$.

Proof. Plainly, from the definition of ω it follows that $\langle r \rangle_\vartheta \subseteq \langle r \rangle_\omega$, for all $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$. Therefore, since $\vartheta \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$, we also have that $\omega \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$. \square

Claim 4.3. $(\forall x)(\omega_x \neq \sigma_x)$.

⁸ Note that this is equivalent to the following condition: "for all classes \mathcal{C} of partial recursive functions, if there exist indices $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\phi_m \in \mathcal{C}$ and $\phi_n \notin \mathcal{C}$, then $\mathbf{I}_\phi^{\mathcal{C}}$ is non-recursive".

Proof. Let $x \in \mathbb{N}$. If $\theta(x) = \mathbf{z}$, then, from the definitions of σ and ω it follows that $\sigma_x = \lambda y.0$ and $\omega_x = \zeta$, and so $\omega_x \neq \sigma_x$. Similarly, if $0 \notin \mathbf{Dom}(\vartheta_x)$, we have that $\omega_x = \perp$ and $\sigma_x = \zeta$, and hence $\omega_x \neq \sigma_x$ again. It remains to consider the case $\theta(x) = n$, with $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{\mathbf{z}\}$. But, in this case, it can readily be verified that $\sigma_x = \zeta$ and also that $(\vartheta_n \not\leq \zeta \implies \omega_x = \vartheta_n) \wedge (\vartheta_n \leq \zeta \implies \omega_x = \perp)$, which clearly imply that $\omega_x \neq \sigma_x$, thus concluding the proof. \square

Now, we define $\psi =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda xy.(x \in \mathbb{E})? \omega \Downarrow r^{-1} : \sigma \Downarrow (r^{-1} \circ \text{pre})]$, where $r =_{\text{Def}} \lambda x.2x$.

Claim 4.4. ψ is universal.

Proof. Simply note that $\psi \Downarrow r = \omega$ and that ω is universal (by Claim 4.1). \square

Claim 4.5. $\psi \notin \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$.

Proof. Let $f =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda x.(x \in \mathbb{E})? \lambda x.(x+1) : \text{pre}]$. Clearly f is a recursive function. Moreover, it is not difficult to verify (using the definition of ψ and Claim 4.3) that $\langle f \rangle_\psi = \emptyset$. Hence $\psi \notin \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$. \square

Claim 4.6. $\psi \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RT}}$.

Proof. Let S be any non-trivial ψ -index set. We must show that S is non-recursive. To begin with, we note that $r^{-1}(S)$ is a ω -index set. In addition, $r^{-1}(S)$ is non-trivial. Indeed, since S is non-trivial, there exist $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $m \in S$ and $n \notin S$. Thus, by Claim 4.1, there exist $m', n' \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\omega_{m'} = \psi_m$ and $\omega_{n'} = \psi_n$. From the very definition of ψ and r , we have that $\psi_{r(m')} = \omega_{m'}$ and $\psi_{r(n')} = \omega_{n'}$, so that $\psi_{r(m')} = \psi_m$ and $\psi_{r(n')} = \psi_n$ hold. Hence, $m' \in r^{-1}(S)$ and $n' \notin r^{-1}(S)$, proving that $r^{-1}(S)$ is a non-trivial ω -index set. By Claim 4.2 and Theorem 3, we have that $\omega \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RT}}$, and so $r^{-1}(S) \in \text{NRec}$, which in turn yields $S \in \text{NRec}$, concluding the proof of the claim. \square

The proof of Theorem 4 now follows from Claims 4.4, 4.5 and 4.6. \square

4 Effectively uniformly non-trivial sequences and their diagonal sets. A characterization of RFPT

In this section we formally define the effectively uniformly non-trivial sequences and their diagonal sets, and present some of their properties, among which the characterization of RFPT mentioned in the introduction (cf. Theorem 6).

Definition 2. Let \mathcal{C} be a sequence, and let ϕ be a ps.

- (1) \mathcal{C} is effectively uniformly non-trivial with respect to ϕ (ϕ -eunt, for short) if there exist $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $(\forall x)(\phi_{a(x)} \in \mathcal{C}_x \wedge \phi_{b(x)} \notin \mathcal{C}_x)$.
In such a case we say that \mathcal{C} is ϕ -eunt via the pair (a, b) .
- (2) The diagonal set of \mathcal{C} relative to ϕ (or ϕ -diagonal set of \mathcal{C} , for short) is the set $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\phi =_{\text{Def}} \{x \in \mathbb{N} : \phi_x \in \mathcal{C}_x\}$.

We denote by \mathfrak{S}_ϕ the class of the ϕ -eunt sequences and by Diags_ϕ the class of the ϕ -diagonal sets of the ϕ -eunt sequences, i.e., $\text{Diags}_\phi =_{\text{Def}} \{\langle\langle \mathcal{U} \rangle\rangle_\phi : \mathcal{U} \in \mathfrak{S}_\phi\}$.

Note that, for all pses ϕ and all apses φ , we have that $\mathfrak{S}_\phi \subseteq \mathfrak{S}_\varphi$.⁹ Moreover, every non-trivial ϕ -index set is a member of the class Diags_ϕ , but not conversely (e.g., in the case of an aps φ , the halting set $\{x \in \mathbb{N} : x \in \mathbf{Dom}(\varphi_x)\}$ is a member of Diags_φ though is not a φ -index set).¹⁰

The following theorem provides a characterization of the ϕ -diagonal sets of the ϕ -eunt sequences, where ϕ is a ps.

Theorem 5. *For all pses ϕ , and all $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (A) $S \in \text{Diags}_\phi$;
- (B) there exist $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that
 - (B1) $\langle a \rangle_\phi \subseteq S$;
 - (B2) $\langle b \rangle_\phi \subseteq \overline{S}$;
 - (B3) $(\forall x)(\phi_{a(x)} \neq \phi_{b(x)})$.

Proof. Suppose that $S \in \text{Diags}_\phi$ and let $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}_\phi$ be such that $S = \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\phi$. Let $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that \mathcal{C} is ϕ -eunt via the pair (a, b) . Then, it is immediate to verify that (B1)–(B3) hold for the pair (a, b) . Conversely, let $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ be such that (B1)–(B3) hold. Consider the sequence \mathcal{C} such that, for all $x \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\mathcal{C}_x =_{\text{Def}} \begin{cases} \{\phi_{a(x)}\}, & \text{if } x \notin S \\ \mathcal{P}^{(1)} \setminus \{\phi_{b(x)}\}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

By (B3), we plainly have that \mathcal{C} is ϕ -eunt via the pair (a, b) . Moreover, from (B1) it follows that $\overline{S} \subseteq \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\phi$, i.e., $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\phi \subseteq S$; similarly, (B2) implies that $S \subseteq \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\phi$. Therefore $S = \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\phi$, with $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}_\phi$, which concludes the proof of the theorem. \square

Next we have the following characterization theorem:

Theorem 6. *For all pses ϕ , the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (A) $\phi \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{RFPT}}$;
- (B) for all $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, $\langle a \rangle_\phi \bowtie \langle b \rangle_\phi$;
- (C) for all $S, T \in \text{Diags}_\phi$, $S \bowtie T$;
- (D) $\text{Diags}_\phi \subseteq \text{NRec}$.

⁹ Indeed, from the definition of an aps, we have that $\phi = \varphi \downarrow r$, for some $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$.

Therefore, if a sequence \mathcal{C} is ϕ -eunt via a pair (a, b) of recursive functions, we have that \mathcal{C} is φ -eunt via the pair $(r \circ a, r \circ b)$. (See also footnote 7.)

¹⁰ In fact, we will see in Section 4.1 that, for an aps φ , the class Diags_φ contains diagonal sets which are not recursively isomorphic to any φ -index set (cf. Theorem 9).

Proof. (A) \implies (B): Suppose that (A) holds, and let $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$. Toward a contradiction, let us assume that there exists a set $S \in \text{Rec}$ separating $\langle a \rangle_\phi$ from $\langle b \rangle_\phi$, i.e., such that $\langle a \rangle_\phi \subseteq S \subseteq \overline{\langle b \rangle_\phi}$, and let $r =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda x.(x \in S) ? b : a]$. Plainly, r is a recursive function, so that, by (A), $\langle r \rangle_\phi \neq \emptyset$. From the definition of r , it follows immediately that $\langle r \rangle_\phi \cap S \subseteq \langle b \rangle_\phi$ and $\langle r \rangle_\phi \cap \overline{S} \subseteq \langle a \rangle_\phi$. These, together with $\langle a \rangle_\phi \subseteq S \subseteq \overline{\langle b \rangle_\phi}$, imply that $\langle r \rangle_\phi = \emptyset$, a contradiction. Thus $\langle a \rangle_\phi$ and $\langle b \rangle_\phi$ are recursively inseparable, i.e., $\langle a \rangle_\phi \bowtie \langle b \rangle_\phi$ holds, proving that (A) \implies (B).

(B) \implies (C): Suppose that (B) holds, and let $S, T \in \text{Diags}_\phi$. By Theorem 5, there exist $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $\langle a \rangle_\phi \subseteq S$ and $\langle b \rangle_\phi \subseteq T$. By (B), we have that $\langle a \rangle_\phi \bowtie \langle b \rangle_\phi$, which in turn implies $S \bowtie T$, as any set that separates S from T also separates every subset of S from every subset of T . Hence (B) \implies (C).

(C) \implies (D): Suppose that (C) holds, and let $S \in \text{Diags}_\phi$. From the characterization of Theorem 5, it follows immediately that the class Diags_ϕ is closed under complementation, so that $\overline{S} \in \text{Diags}_\phi$. Thus, by (C), we have that $S \bowtie \overline{S}$, which plainly implies that $S \in \text{NRec}$, proving that (C) \implies (D).

(D) \implies (A): Suppose that (D) holds. Toward a contradiction, let us also assume that there exists a recursive function $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $\langle r \rangle_\phi = \emptyset$. Then, by putting $S =_{\text{Def}} \emptyset$, $a =_{\text{Def}} r$ and $b =_{\text{Def}} \lambda x.x$ (the identity function), we have that $\langle a \rangle_\phi \subseteq S$, $\langle b \rangle_\phi \subseteq \overline{S}$ and $(\forall x)(\phi_{a(x)} \neq \phi_{b(x)})$. Since $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, Theorem 5 yields $\emptyset = S \in \text{Diags}_\phi$, so that, by (D), $\emptyset \in \text{NRec}$, which is a contradiction. Thus, (D) \implies (A) holds, concluding the proof of the theorem. \square

From Theorems 2 and 6, we obtain:

Corollary 1. *For all apses φ , the following properties hold:*

- (A) for all $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, $\langle a \rangle_\varphi \bowtie \langle b \rangle_\varphi$;
- (B) for all $S, T \in \text{Diags}_\varphi$, $S \bowtie T$;
- (C) $\text{Diags}_\varphi \subseteq \text{NRec}$.

Since, as remarked before, for all pses ϕ , the class Diags_ϕ contains all of the non-trivial ϕ -index sets, the above corollary generalizes Theorem 1.¹¹

4.1 Recursive Isomorphisms of Diagonal Sets

We present now some results concerning recursive isomorphisms of φ -diagonal sets of φ -eunt sequences, where φ is an **aps**. In particular, we will show that:

- (P1) the isomorphism type of Diags_φ is *independent* of φ , i.e., for all apses ψ , $\text{Iso}(\text{Diags}_\varphi) = \text{Iso}(\text{Diags}_\psi)$ (cf. Theorem 7);¹²
- (P2) every r.e. diagonal set in the class Diags_φ is φ -creative (cf. Theorem 8),¹³ and hence recursively isomorphic to the index set $\overline{\mathbf{I}}_\varphi$;

¹¹ In the next section we will prove a strengthening of (A) of this corollary (cf. Lemma 1), which generalizes a result of Hay [2, Corollary 1.1.].

¹² Notice, however, that we do not have $\text{Diags}_\varphi = \text{Diags}_\psi$, for all apses φ and ψ (see Remark 2).

¹³ This result is a generalization of [2, Theorem 5.].

(P3) Diags_φ contains a diagonal set which is recursively isomorphic to its complement (cf. Theorem 9).

Let us notice immediately the following consequence of (P3). Since no φ -index set can be recursively isomorphic to its complement (as it follows easily by Theorem 2), and since the relation \equiv is transitive and respects complements (i.e., $A \equiv B \implies \overline{A} \equiv \overline{B}$, for any two sets A and B), by (P3) we have that there exists a diagonal set $S \in \text{Diags}_\varphi$ such that S is not recursively isomorphic to any φ -index set. Therefore, the isomorphism type of Diags_φ is strictly larger than the isomorphism type of the class of the non-trivial φ -index sets.

We begin with (P1). We have:

Theorem 7. *For all apses φ and ψ , $\text{Iso}(\text{Diags}_\varphi) = \text{Iso}(\text{Diags}_\psi)$.*

Proof. Clearly, it is enough to prove that $\text{Diags}_\varphi \subseteq \text{Iso}(\text{Diags}_\psi)$. So, suppose that $S \in \text{Diags}_\varphi$, and let $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}_\varphi$ such that $S = \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\varphi$. Let $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that \mathcal{C} is φ -eunt via the pair (a, b) . By Rogers' Isomorphism Theorem, let j be a recursive permutation such that $\varphi = \psi \parallel j$. Consider the sequence \mathcal{U} such that, for each $x \in \mathbb{N}$, $\mathcal{U}_x =_{\text{Def}} \mathcal{C}_{j^{-1}(x)}$. It is easy to verify that \mathcal{U} is ψ -eunt via the pair $(j \circ (a \circ j^{-1}), j \circ (b \circ j^{-1}))$ and moreover that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\varphi = j^{-1}(\langle\langle \mathcal{U} \rangle\rangle_\psi)$, i.e., $S = j^{-1}(\langle\langle \mathcal{U} \rangle\rangle_\psi)$. Thus, $S \equiv \langle\langle \mathcal{U} \rangle\rangle_\psi \in \text{Diags}_\psi$, so that $S \in \text{Iso}(\text{Diags}_\psi)$. Hence $\text{Diags}_\varphi \subseteq \text{Iso}(\text{Diags}_\psi)$. \square

Remark 2. Note that, for all apses φ , there exists an aps ψ such that $\text{Diags}_\varphi \not\subseteq \text{Diags}_\psi$. For, let $r =_{\text{Def}} \text{PrimRec}^*(\text{pad}(n, 0), \lambda xy. \text{pad}(n, y))$, where pad is a padding function for φ and $n \in \overline{\mathbf{I}}_\varphi^\perp$. Clearly r is an increasing recursive function; moreover we have that $(\forall x)(\varphi_{r(x)} = \varphi_n)$. Let $\psi =_{\text{Def}} \varphi \parallel r^{-1}$. Since $\psi \parallel r = \varphi$, plainly, ψ is an aps. We claim that there is no $a \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $\langle a \rangle_\psi \subseteq \mathbf{I}_\varphi^\perp$, and therefore, by Theorem 5, $\mathbf{I}_\varphi^\perp \notin \text{Diags}_\psi$ which in turn implies that $\text{Diags}_\varphi \not\subseteq \text{Diags}_\psi$. For, suppose, toward a contradiction, that there is $a \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $\langle a \rangle_\psi \subseteq \mathbf{I}_\varphi^\perp$. By Kleene's Recursion Theorem, let $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\varphi_m = \psi_{a(r(m))}$. Then we have that $r(m) \in \langle a \rangle_\psi$, and so $r(m) \in \mathbf{I}_\varphi^\perp$. But this is a contradiction, since $\varphi_{r(m)} = \varphi_n$, with $\varphi_n \neq \perp$. The contradiction proves our claim.

Next we turn to (P2). First of all, we prove the following lemma.

Lemma 1. *For all apses φ and all $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, we have that $\langle a \rangle_\varphi \dot{\not\sqsubseteq}_\varphi \langle b \rangle_\varphi$.*

Proof. Let conv be a convergence predicate for φ (cf. Proposition 1) and let

$$\omega =_{\text{Def}} \lambda xyzuv. (u \cdot \text{conv}(x, z, \sigma(x, y, z)) + v \cdot \text{conv}(y, z, \sigma(x, y, z))),$$

where $\sigma =_{\text{Def}} \lambda xyz. \mu t (\text{conv}(x, z, t) + \text{conv}(y, z, t) \neq 0)$. Plainly, $\omega \in \mathcal{P}^{(5)}$; thus, by the s - m - n Theorem, there exists $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(2)}$ such that

$$\varphi \parallel r = \lambda xyz. \omega(\pi'(x), \pi''(x), y, \varphi(b(y), z), \varphi(a(y), z)).$$

It is not difficult to verify that

$$(\forall x)(\forall y)(y \in (\mathbf{Dom}(\varphi_{\pi'(x)}) \setminus \mathbf{Dom}(\varphi_{\pi''(x)})) \implies \varphi_{r(x,y)} = \varphi_{b(y)} \quad (1)$$

$$(\forall x)(\forall y)(y \in (\mathbf{Dom}(\varphi_{\pi''(x)}) \setminus \mathbf{Dom}(\varphi_{\pi'(x)})) \implies \varphi_{r(x,y)} = \varphi_{a(y)} \quad (2)$$

both hold. By the Fixed Point Theorem with Parameters, let $\text{fix} \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that

$$(\forall x)(\varphi_{\text{fix}(x)} = \varphi_{r(x,\text{fix}(x))}) \quad (3)$$

and let $k =_{\text{Def}} \lambda xy.\text{fix}(\pi(x,y))$. Then, from (1), (2) and (3), it easily follows that k is a Kleene function for the pair $(\langle a \rangle_\varphi, \langle b \rangle_\varphi)$ relative to φ , and so $\langle a \rangle_\varphi \triangleleft_\varphi \langle b \rangle_\varphi$. \square

Theorem 8. *For all apses φ and all $S \in \text{Diags}_\varphi$, if S is r.e. then \bar{S} is φ -productive, and hence S is φ -creative.*

Proof. Suppose that $S \in \text{Diags}_\varphi$ is r.e. and let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\mathbf{Dom}(\varphi_n) = S$. By Theorem 5 and Lemma 1, let $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ and $k \in \mathcal{R}^{(2)}$ such that $\langle a \rangle_\varphi \subseteq S$, $\langle b \rangle_\varphi \subseteq \bar{S}$ and k is a Kleene function for the pair $(\langle a \rangle_\varphi, \langle b \rangle_\varphi)$ relative to φ . Then, let $p =_{\text{Def}} \lambda x.k(n, x)$. It can easily be verified that p is in fact a φ -productive function for \bar{S} , so that \bar{S} is φ -productive, as required. \square

Finally, we show that (P3) holds. We have:

Theorem 9. *For all apses φ , there exists $S \in \text{Diags}_\varphi$ such that $S \equiv \bar{S}$.*

Proof. Let $f =_{\text{Def}} \text{PrimRec}^*(\text{pad}(0, 0), \lambda xy.\text{pad}(x+1, y))$, where pad is a padding function for φ . Clearly, $f \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$. Moreover, the following two properties can be verified easily

$$(\forall x)(\varphi_{f(x)} = \varphi_x) \quad (4)$$

$$(\forall x)(f(x+1) > f(x) > x). \quad (5)$$

Let $\psi =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda xy.(y \in \mathbf{Ran}(f)) ? \lambda xy.\vartheta(x, f^{-1}(y)) + 1 : \lambda xy.0]$. Since $\psi \in \mathcal{P}^{(2)}$, by Kleene's Recursion Theorem, there exists an $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\vartheta_n = \psi_n$. Let $g =_{\text{Def}} \vartheta_n$. Clearly, we have

$$(\forall x)(x \notin \mathbf{Ran}(f) \implies g(x) = 0). \quad (6)$$

In addition, since by (5) f is injective, we also have that

$$(\forall x)(g(f(x)) = g(x) + 1). \quad (7)$$

From (6) and (7), and since $0 \notin \mathbf{Ran}(f)$, it follows that g is total, so it is a recursive function. Then, let $h =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda x.(g(x) \in \mathbb{E}) ? f : f^{-1}]$. Using (6), (7) and (5), it can be verified, without any particular difficulty, that h is total—and hence recursive—and moreover that

$$(\forall x)(f(h(x)) \in \{x, f(f(x))\}), \quad (8)$$

$$(\forall x)(g(x) \in \mathbb{E} \iff g(h(x)) \notin \mathbb{E}) \quad (9)$$

and

$$(\forall x)(h(h(x)) = x). \quad (10)$$

From (10), it follows that h is both surjective and injective, thus h is a recursive permutation. Also, (4) and (8) imply that

$$(\forall x)(\varphi_{h(x)} = \varphi_x). \quad (11)$$

Next, let \mathcal{C} be the sequence such that, for all $x \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\mathcal{C}_x =_{\text{def}} \begin{cases} \{\perp\}, & \text{if } g(x) \in \mathbb{E} \\ \mathcal{P}^{(1)} \setminus \{\perp\}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

By using (9), we obtain

$$(\forall x)(\mathcal{C}_{h(x)} = \mathcal{P}^{(1)} \setminus \mathcal{C}_x). \quad (12)$$

Let $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that

$$\varphi \Vdash a = [\lambda xy.(g(x) \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \mathbb{E}) ? \lambda xy.0] \quad \text{and} \quad \varphi \Vdash b = [\lambda xy.(g(x) \in \mathbb{E}) ? \lambda xy.0].$$

Plainly, from the definition of \mathcal{C} and the latter two equalities, it follows that \mathcal{C} is φ -eunt via the pair (a, b) ; moreover, (11) and (12) imply that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\varphi = h^{-1}(\overline{\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\varphi})$. Thus, putting $S =_{\text{def}} \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\varphi$, we have that $S \in \text{Diags}_\varphi$ and that S is recursively isomorphic to \overline{S} via the recursive permutation h , concluding the proof of the theorem. \square

5 Conclusions

We have shown that, in the context of universal programming systems, Rice's Theorem is strictly weaker than Rogers' Fixed Point Theorem. We have introduced the effectively uniformly non-trivial sequences of classes of partial recursive functions and their diagonal sets, and we have observed that Rogers' Fixed Point Theorem is equivalent to the effective inseparability of such diagonal sets. Some properties concerning recursive isomorphisms of these diagonal sets have been presented and discussed as well.

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6 Appendix: further properties of diagonal sets of effectively uniformly non-trivial sequences of classes of partial recursive functions

Note. Throughout this appendix we use the following notations:

(I) \mathfrak{S} denotes the class of the sequences \mathcal{C} such that, for some pses α and β ,

$$(\forall x)((\alpha_x \in \mathcal{C}_x) \wedge (\beta_x \notin \mathcal{C}_x)).$$

Plainly, observe that, from the definition of *aps*, it follows that $\mathfrak{S} = \mathfrak{S}_\varphi$, for all *apses* φ .

(II) *APS* denotes the class of the *apses*.

Also, whenever needed, we will (tacitly) use the following simple property, which is an immediate consequence of the definition of *aps* given in Section 2 and the first property mentioned in footnote 7:

“for all pses ϕ , $\phi \in \mathcal{APS}$ iff there exists $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $\phi \parallel r \in \mathcal{APS}$ ”.

Given an *aps* φ and a sequence $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}$, by Corollary 1.(C), the diagonal set $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\varphi$ is non-recursive.¹⁴ If r is a given recursive function, what about the (non-)recursiveness of the diagonal set $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r}$? Does this diagonal set belong to the class Diags_φ ? In this appendix we present some results concerning these questions.

Preliminarily, we introduce the following definitions.

Definition 3. Let $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, and let \mathcal{C} be a sequence. Then,

- (1) r is suitable if $\overline{\text{Ran}(r)}$ contains no infinite r.e. subsets;
- (2) \mathcal{C} is semi-recursive if, for all $f \in \mathcal{P}^{(1)}$, $\|\mathcal{C}\|_f \in \text{Rec}$, where

$$\|\mathcal{C}\|_f =_{\text{def}} \{x \in \mathbb{N} : f \in \mathcal{C}_x\}.$$

We will prove that the suitable recursive functions coincide precisely with the recursive functions r such that, for all $(\varphi, \mathcal{C}) \in \mathcal{APS} \times \mathfrak{S}$, the diagonal set $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r}$ is non-recursive (cf. Theorem 10), and we will see that there exist suitable recursive functions r and sequences $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}$ such that, for some *apses* φ and ψ , $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r} \in \text{Diags}_\varphi$ but $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\psi \parallel r} \notin \text{Diags}_\psi$ (see Example 1).

Also, a characterization will be provided of the pairs $(r, \mathcal{C}) \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)} \times \mathfrak{S}$ such that, for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$, $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r} \in \text{Rec}$ (cf. Theorem 12). These are precisely the pairs (r, \mathcal{C}) where r has finite range and \mathcal{C} is semi-recursive. We will see that there exist in fact sequences in \mathfrak{S} which are not semi-recursive (cf. Theorem 13) and deduce that there are no recursive functions r such that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r} \in \text{Rec}$, for $(\varphi, \mathcal{C}) \in \mathcal{APS} \times \mathfrak{S}$.

Finally, we present some results involving non-suitable injective recursive functions. Specifically, if r is a non-suitable injective recursive function then,

¹⁴ In fact, as observed in the note above, $\mathfrak{S} = \mathfrak{S}_\varphi$, and thus $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_\varphi \in \text{Diags}_\varphi$.

for all $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}$, there exist **apses** φ and ψ such that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \downarrow r} \in \text{Rec}$ (and hence $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \downarrow r} \notin \text{Diags}_{\varphi}$) and $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\psi \downarrow r} \in \text{Diags}_{\psi}$ (and hence $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\psi \downarrow r} \in \text{NRec}$) (cf. Theorems 14 and 15).

We have:

Theorem 10. *For all $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (A) for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$ and all $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}$, $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \downarrow r} \in \text{NRec}$;
- (B) for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$, $\mathbf{I}_{\varphi \downarrow r}^{\perp} \in \text{NRec}$;
- (C) r is suitable;
- (D) for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$, $\varphi \downarrow r \in \mathcal{APS}$.

Proof. Let $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$. Plainly, we have that (A) \implies (B); moreover, by Corollary 1, (D) \implies (A). So we turn to the remaining implications.

We begin by proving that (B) \implies (C) holds. So, suppose that (B) holds i.e., $\mathbf{I}_{\varphi \downarrow r}^{\perp} \in \text{NRec}$, for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$. We must show that r is suitable, i.e., $\overline{\mathbf{Ran}(r)}$ contains no infinite r.e. subset. We proceed as follows. Toward a contradiction, let us assume that there exists an infinite r.e. set S such that $S \subseteq \overline{\mathbf{Ran}(r)}$. Since S is infinite and r.e., there exists an injective recursive function s such that $S = \mathbf{Ran}(s)$. Let $\psi =_{\text{def}} \boldsymbol{\vartheta} \downarrow s^{-1}$. Since $\psi \downarrow s = \boldsymbol{\vartheta}$, we have that ψ is an **aps**. Moreover, since $\mathbf{Ran}(s) = S \subseteq \overline{\mathbf{Ran}(r)}$, we also have that $\mathbf{I}_{\psi \downarrow r}^{\perp} = \mathbb{N} \in \text{Rec}$, contradicting (B). Thus, $\overline{\mathbf{Ran}(r)}$ contains no infinite r.e. subset.

Next we prove that (C) \implies (D). Suppose that (C) holds, i.e., $\overline{\mathbf{Ran}(r)}$ contains no infinite r.e. subset, and let φ be an arbitrary **aps** and $\psi =_{\text{def}} \varphi \downarrow r$. We must show that ψ is an **aps**. So, let **pad** be a padding function for φ , and let

$$f =_{\text{def}} \lambda x. \mu y (\text{pad}(x, \pi'(y)) = r(\pi''(y))).$$

Notice that, for all $x \in \mathbf{Dom}(f)$, $r(\pi''(f(x))) = \text{pad}(x, \pi'(f(x)))$ and thus $\psi_{\pi''(f(x))} = \varphi_x$. Hence, in order to prove that ψ is an **aps**, it is enough to show that the function f is total,¹⁵ which we do as follows. Let $x \in \mathbb{N}$ be fixed. Then $S = \{\text{pad}(x, y) : y \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is an infinite r.e. set, and hence S cannot be a subset of $\overline{\mathbf{Ran}(r)}$. So, there exist $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\text{pad}(x, n) = r(m)$. Putting $y =_{\text{def}} \pi(n, m)$, we have that $\text{pad}(x, \pi'(y)) = r(\pi''(y))$ and therefore $x \in \mathbf{Dom}(f)$. \square

Example 1. Let \mathcal{C} be the sequence such that, for all $x \in \mathbb{N}$, $\mathcal{C}_x = \{\perp\}$, and let $r =_{\text{def}} \lambda x. x + 1$. Clearly $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}$ and r is suitable. We show that there exist $\varphi, \psi \in \mathcal{APS}$ such that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \downarrow r} \in \text{Diags}_{\varphi}$ and $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\psi \downarrow r} \notin \text{Diags}_{\psi}$.

Indeed, let **conv** be a convergence predicate for $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$ and let φ and ψ the **apses** such that, for all $x \in \mathbb{N}$,

- (I) $\varphi_{2x} = \psi_{2x} = \boldsymbol{\vartheta}_x$,
- (II) $\varphi_{2x+1} = [\lambda y. (\exists z)(\text{conv}(x, 0, z) = 1) ? \lambda x. 0]$,
- (III) $\psi_{2x+1} = \lambda x. 0$.

¹⁵ cf. the property mentioned in the note at the beginning of the section.

It is easy to verify that $\mathbf{I}_\varphi^{[\lambda x.(x>0)?\lambda x.1]} \subseteq \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r}$ and that $\mathbf{I}_\varphi^{\lambda x.1} \subseteq \overline{\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r}}$, and so, by Theorem 5, we have that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r} \in \mathbf{Diags}_\varphi$. We claim that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\psi \parallel r} \notin \mathbf{Diags}_\psi$, which we prove as follows. Toward a contradiction, let us assume that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\psi \parallel r} \in \mathbf{Diags}_\psi$. Then there exists $a \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $\langle a \rangle_\psi \subseteq \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\psi \parallel r}$. By Kleene's Recursion Theorem, there exists an $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\vartheta_n = \psi_{a(2n)}$. Using (I), the latter yields $\psi_{2n} = \psi_{a(2n)}$ and therefore we have that

$$2n \in \langle a \rangle_\psi \implies 2n \in \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\psi \parallel r} \implies \psi_{2n+1} = \perp \implies \lambda x.0 = \perp$$

which is a contradiction. Thus $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\psi \parallel r} \notin \mathbf{Diags}_\psi$, as claimed.

Next, we characterize the pairs $(r, \mathcal{C}) \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)} \times \mathfrak{S}$ such that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r} \in \mathbf{Rec}$, for all **aps** φ . We have:

Lemma 2. *Let $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $\mathbf{Ran}(r)$ is infinite. Then there exists an **aps** φ such that $\varphi \parallel r \in \mathcal{APS}$.*

Proof. Let us put

$$s =_{\text{Def}} \mathbf{PrimRec}^*(0, \lambda y. \mu z (r(z) > r(y))) \quad \text{and} \quad t =_{\text{Def}} r \circ s.$$

Plainly, $s, t \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$; moreover t is increasing. Let $\varphi =_{\text{Def}} \vartheta \parallel t^{-1}$. It is immediate to verify that $\varphi \parallel t = (\varphi \parallel r) \parallel s = \vartheta$, so that $\varphi, \varphi \parallel r \in \mathcal{APS}$. \square

Theorem 11. *Let $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$. The following conditions are equivalent:*

- (A) $\mathbf{Ran}(r)$ is finite;
- (B) for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$ and all semi-recursive sequences \mathcal{C} , $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r} \in \mathbf{Rec}$;
- (C) for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$, $\mathbf{I}_{\varphi \parallel r}^\perp \in \mathbf{Rec}$;
- (D) for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$, $\varphi \parallel r \notin \mathcal{APS}$.

Proof. Plainly, (B) \implies (C) and (C) \implies (D) hold. Moreover, by Lemma 2, we have that (D) \implies (A). Thus we only need to show that (A) \implies (B) holds as well. So, suppose that $\mathbf{Ran}(r)$ is finite. Let φ be an **aps** and \mathcal{C} a semi-recursive sequence. Since $\mathbf{Ran}(r)$ is finite, the class $\{\varphi_{r(x)} : x \in \mathbb{N}\}$ contains only finitely many distinct partial recursive functions, say the functions f_0, f_1, \dots, f_n , with $n \geq 0$. Let $S_i =_{\text{Def}} r^{-1}(\mathbf{Ran}(r) \cap \mathbf{I}_\varphi^{f_i})$, for $0 \leq i \leq n$. It is not difficult to verify that

$$\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r} = \bigcup_{0 \leq i \leq n} (S_i \cap \|\mathcal{C}\|_{f_i}). \quad (13)$$

Since r is recursive and $\mathbf{Ran}(r)$ is finite, each set S_i is plainly recursive and therefore, by the semi-recursive nature of \mathcal{C} , we have that $S_i \cap \|\mathcal{C}\|_{f_i} \in \mathbf{Rec}$, for $0 \leq i \leq n$. Thus, by (13), we have that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r} \in \mathbf{Rec}$, which shows, in fact, that (A) \implies (B) holds, concluding the proof of the theorem. \square

Theorem 12. *For all $(r, \mathcal{C}) \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)} \times \mathfrak{S}$, the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (A) for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$, $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \parallel r} \in \mathbf{Rec}$;

(B) $\mathbf{Ran}(r)$ is finite and \mathcal{C} is semi-recursive.

Proof. From Theorem 11, we plainly have that (B) \implies (A) holds. In order to prove that the converse implication holds as well, let us assume (A). Then, by Lemma 2 and Corollary 1, $\mathbf{Ran}(r)$ is finite. Hence, there exists $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\mathbf{Ran}(r) \subseteq \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$. It remains to prove that \mathcal{C} is semi-recursive, i.e., that $\|\mathcal{C}\|_f \in \mathbf{Rec}$, for all $f \in \mathcal{P}^{(1)}$. Thus, let $f \in \mathcal{P}^{(1)}$ and put

$$\varphi^f =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda xy.(x \leq n) ? \lambda xy.f(y) : \lambda xy.\vartheta(s(x), y)],$$

where $s =_{\text{Def}} \lambda x.\mu t(n+1+t=x)$. It is easy to verify that $\varphi^f \Vdash \lambda x.(x+n+1) = \vartheta$, so that $\varphi^f \in \mathcal{APS}$. Moreover, we also have that $(\forall x)(\varphi_{r(x)}^f = f)$. Hence $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi^f \Vdash r} = \|\mathcal{C}\|_f$ and therefore, by (A), $\|\mathcal{C}\|_f \in \mathbf{Rec}$, completing the proof that \mathcal{C} is semi-recursive. \square

An immediate consequence of the above theorem is that, if there exist some sequence $\mathcal{U} \in \mathfrak{S}$ which is not semi-recursive, then there is no recursive function $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that, for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$ and $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}$, $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \Vdash r} \in \mathbf{Rec}$. And in fact, we can prove a more general result which, together with Corollary 1, immediately implies the existence of such sequences which are not semi-recursive. We have:

Theorem 13. *There exists $\mathcal{U} \in \mathfrak{S}$ such that, for all pses ϕ for which the class $\mathcal{P}_\phi =_{\text{Def}} \{\phi_x : x \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is finite, $\langle\langle \mathcal{U} \rangle\rangle_\phi \in \mathbf{Diags}_\vartheta$.*

Proof. Let $\alpha =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda xy.(\mathbf{Dom}(\vartheta_x) \not\subseteq \{x\}) ? \vartheta]$ and let \mathcal{U} be the sequence such that $\mathcal{U}_x =_{\text{Def}} \{\alpha_x\}$, for each $x \in \mathbb{N}$. Putting $\beta =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda xy.(y=x) ? \lambda xy.0]$, it can be readily verified that $(\forall x)(\alpha_x \in \mathcal{U}_x \wedge \beta_x \notin \mathcal{U}_x)$ holds, so that $\mathcal{U} \in \mathfrak{S}$. Next, let ϕ be any ps such that the class \mathcal{P}_ϕ is finite. We claim that $\langle\langle \mathcal{U} \rangle\rangle_\phi \in \mathbf{Diags}_\vartheta$, which we prove as follows. To begin with, note that

$$(\forall x)(\vartheta_x = \alpha_x \iff \mathbf{Dom}(\vartheta_x) \neq \{x\}). \quad (14)$$

Since \mathcal{P}_ϕ is finite, there plainly exists a $q \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$(\forall x)(x \geq q \implies \mathbf{Dom}(\phi_x) \not\subseteq \{\{x\}, \{x+1\}\}). \quad (15)$$

Moreover, since ϑ is an **aps**, there are indices m and n such that

$$(\vartheta_m \neq \vartheta_n) \wedge (\forall x)(x < q \implies \vartheta_x \notin \{\vartheta_m, \vartheta_n\}). \quad (16)$$

Let $a, b \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \vartheta \Vdash a &= [\lambda xy.(x \geq q) ? \phi : \lambda xy.\vartheta(m, y)] \\ \vartheta \Vdash b &= [\lambda xy.((x \geq q) \wedge (y = x+1)) ? \lambda xy.0 : [\lambda xy.(x < q) ? \lambda xy.\vartheta(n, y)]] \end{aligned}$$

Then, by using (14), (15) and (16), it is no difficult to verify that $\langle a \rangle_\vartheta \subseteq \langle\langle \mathcal{U} \rangle\rangle_\phi$, $\langle b \rangle_\vartheta \subseteq \overline{\langle\langle \mathcal{U} \rangle\rangle_\phi}$, and $(\forall x)(\vartheta_{a(x)} \neq \vartheta_{b(x)})$ hold, so that, by Theorem 5, $\langle\langle \mathcal{U} \rangle\rangle_\phi \in \mathbf{Diags}_\vartheta$ follows, as claimed. \square

We conclude this appendix with some results involving non-suitable injective recursive functions.

Lemma 3. *For all non-suitable injective recursive functions $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ and all pses ϕ , there exists $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$ such that $\varphi \Downarrow r = \phi$.*

Proof. Let $f \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ such that $\vartheta \Downarrow f = \phi$. Since r is non-suitable, there exists an infinite recursive set S such that $S \subseteq \overline{\mathbf{Ran}(r)}$. Let s be an injective recursive function such that $\mathbf{Ran}(s) = S$. Then, if we put

$$\varphi =_{\text{Def}} \vartheta \Downarrow [\lambda x.(x \in S) ? s^{-1} : f \circ r^{-1}],$$

it can easily be verified that $\varphi \Downarrow s = \vartheta$ —so that $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$ —and that $\varphi \Downarrow r = \phi$, as required. \square

Theorem 14. *For all non-suitable injective recursive functions $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$ and all $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}$, there exists $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$ such that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \Downarrow r} \in \text{Rec}$.*

Proof. Since $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}$, there exists $\alpha \in \mathcal{P}^{(2)}$ such that $(\forall x)(\alpha_x \in \mathcal{C}_x)$. Moreover, since r is non-suitable and injective, by Lemma 3, there exists $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$ such that $\varphi \Downarrow r = \alpha$. Then note that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \Downarrow r} = \mathbb{N}$, which is a recursive set. \square

Lemma 4. *For all non-suitable injective recursive functions $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, there exists an aps φ such that $\varphi \Downarrow r = \varphi$.*

Proof. Since r is non-suitable, there exists an increasing recursive function s such that $\mathbf{Ran}(s) \subseteq \overline{\mathbf{Ran}(r)}$. Let

$$\omega =_{\text{Def}} [\lambda xy.(y \in \mathbf{Ran}(s)) ? \lambda xy.s^{-1}(y) : \lambda xy.\vartheta(x, r^{-1}(y))].$$

Then ω is a ps, so that, by Kleene's Recursion Theorem, there exists an index $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\vartheta_n = \omega_n$. Let $f =_{\text{Def}} \vartheta_n$. Note that, for all $x \in \mathbb{N}$, (I) $f(s(x)) = x$, and (II) $f(r(x)) = f(x)$. Let $\varphi =_{\text{Def}} \vartheta \Downarrow f$. From (I), it plainly follows that $(\forall x)(\varphi_{s(x)} = \vartheta_x)$, i.e., $\varphi \Downarrow s = \vartheta$, and so φ is an aps. By (II), we have that $(\forall x)(\varphi_{r(x)} = \varphi_x)$, i.e., $\varphi \Downarrow r = \varphi$, which concludes the proof of the lemma. \square

Theorem 15. *For all non-suitable injective recursive functions $r \in \mathcal{R}^{(1)}$, and all $\mathcal{C} \in \mathfrak{S}$, there exists $\varphi \in \mathcal{APS}$ such that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \Downarrow r} \in \text{Diags}_{\varphi}$.*

Proof. Let r be a non-suitable injective recursive function. By Lemma 4, there exist an aps φ such that $\varphi \Downarrow r = \varphi$. Then we have that $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \Downarrow r} = \langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi}$, and therefore $\langle\langle \mathcal{C} \rangle\rangle_{\varphi \Downarrow r} \in \text{Diags}_{\varphi}$. \square